

Benzoyl-*m*-Nitro-Acetanilide as A Gravimetric Reagent for Cadmium

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Cadmium (14-23 mg) has been quantitatively precipitated with benzoyl-*m*-nitro-acetanilide and the highly insoluble yellow-coloured bis complex has been dried at 110° for weighing. The conversion factor is 0.1656. The relative standard deviation is $\pm 0.14\%$. Separation from Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, Zn²⁺, Mn²⁺, Pb²⁺, Mg²⁺, Al³⁺, In³⁺ and Cr³⁺ was possible using sodium or magnesium-EDTA as the masking agent. Thermogravimetric studies indicated the complex to be stable upto 410°.

VERY few gravimetric methods for cadmium have been reported and due to its softness this metal ion shows preference to ligands such as amines, cyanides and sulphide ions. Thus thiourea-Reinecke's salt^{1,2} method has been used widely though the accuracy is $\pm 0.4\%$ and several sulphide group metals interfere.

Among the other reagents recommended 2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-benzoxazole³, 1-phenyltetrazoline-5-thione⁴ and 1-immino-3-thioisindoline⁵ may be mentioned but all of these have serious limitations due to interference by other metal ions. However N-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid⁶ has been reported to be selective in acidic medium.

In this investigation benzoyl-*m*-nitro acetanilide has been used in the gravimetric determination of cadmium. The bis-complex is thermally stable and is quite selective when the diverse ions are masked with sodium- or magnesium-ethylenediamine tetracetate (Na₂-EDTA or Mg-EDTA). The precipitation is instantaneous and filtration is easy.

Experimental

Benzoyl-*m*-nitro-acetanilide: The reagent was prepared⁷ by the condensation of ethyl benzoate and *m*-nitroaniline. The reagent has recently been marketed by Polysciences, Inc, U.S.A. Fresh solutions were prepared by dissolving 0.17 to 0.18 of the reagent in 15 ml of aqueous ethanol for each determination.

Cadmium solution: A stock solution was prepared by dissolving hydrated cadmium sulphate (G.R., E. Merck) in dilute sulphuric acid and the metal content was determined using thiourea (Reinecke's salt method^{1,2}).

Diverse ion solution: Aqueous solutions of the desired metal ions were prepared from their nitrates, sulphates and chlorides and a little acid was added where necessary.

Magnesium-EDTA solution: Magnesium chloride (0.1M) and Na₂-EDTA (0.1 M) solutions were prepared separately and 20 ml portions of each were mixed when required.

Apparatus: A Cambridge pH Meter was used for the measurement of pH. A photorecording Metriplex Derivatograph OD-102 (Hungary) was used for the thermogravimetric studies.

Procedure: Dilute an aliquot of the stock cadmium (15-25 mg) solution to 200 ml with water and heat on a water bath to 80-90°. Add the alcoholic solution of the reagent (0.17-0.18g) slowly with steady stirring. Adjust the pH to 6.8 to 7.8 with aqueous ammonia (2 M). Digest the yellow precipitate which was formed immediately on a hot water bath for 20-30 minutes with occasional stirring. Filter the complex through a G4 sintered glass crucible, wash first with hot (80-90°) water and finally with hot aqueous ethanol (30%). Dry at 110-120°. The conversion factor is 0.1656.

When cadmium is to be determined in the presence of diverse ions, add 40 ml of 0.1M magnesium-EDTA, before adding the reagent and maintain the final pH between 7.0 and 7.5.

The results for the determination of cadmium are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF CADMIUM

Wt. taken (mg)	Wt. of the complex (mg)	Cd. found (mg)	Relative Error (%)
14.0	85.9, 85.9	14.2 ₂ , 14.2 ₇	+0.15, +0.15
19.6	118.2, 118.6	19.5 ₇ , 19.6 ₄	-0.15, +0.15
22.4	135.2, 135.6	22.4 ₀ , 22.4 ₄	nil, +0.26

Results and Discussions

The nature of the complex: The brilliant yellow coloured complex has appreciable solubility in chloroform though practically insoluble in aqueous ethanol. The pure complex dried at 115°, was analysed for the metal content by converting a known weight of it to cadmium sulphate before estimation with thiourea Reinecke's salt method. It was analysed for nitrogen by Duma's method. The results

Found Cd = 26.25% N = 8.1%

Calculated for $\text{Cd}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)_2$ Cd = 16.56%
N = 8.2% indicated the formula of a bis-complex.

Thermogravimetric studied: A known weight of the oven dried complex was mixed with aluminium oxide and heated at the rate of 12° per minute. The complex started decomposing at 310° and this exothermic change was sharp at 410° recording a loss of 3.7% in weight. Another less sharp exothermic change was noted at 515°. Finally, at 900° the total

Effect of sequestering agents: Sulphosalicylate, tartarate and citrate prevented the precipitation of cadmium complex. The precipitation was partial in the presence of ascorbate, iodide and fluoride. However, sodium or magnesium-EDTA did not interfere in the determination of cadmium with benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide. Magnesium-EDTA was used in preference to sodium-EDTA as a masking agent during separation of cadmium from various other ions as the nature of the $\text{Cd}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)_2$ precipitated was better for filtration than in the presence of $\text{Na}_2\text{-EDTA}$.

Effect of diverse ions: Quantitative precipitation of cadmium in the presence of nickel(II), cobalt(II), zinc(II), lead(II), magnesium(II), manganese(II), bismuth(III), aluminium(III), chromium(III) and indium(III) was possible by masking these ions with magnesium-EDTA. The results of these separations are presented in Table 2.

Precision and accuracy: The relative standard deviation of this method was calculated to be $\pm 0.14\%$ and the 95% confidence limit of the average was 22.35 ± 0.02 mg.

TABLE 2--SEPARATION OF CADMIUM FROM DIVERSE IONS

Cd. taken (mg)	Diverse ion* (mg)	Wt. of complex (mg)	Cd. found (mg)	Rel. error (%)
19.6	Ni ²⁺ , 20	117.9, 118.0	19.5 ₈ , 19.5 ₄	-0.35, -0.30
19.6	Co ²⁺ , 20	117.6, 117.8	19.4 ₇ , 19.5 ₁	-0.52, -0.45
22.4	Zn ²⁺ , 25	134.9, 134.9	22.3 ₈ , 22.3 ₃	-0.22, -0.22
22.4	Pb ²⁺ , 25	135.2, 134.9	22.4 ₀ , 22.3 ₈	nil, -0.22
22.4	Bi ³⁺ , 20	135.1, 135.2	22.3 ₈ , 22.4 ₈	-0.08, nil
19.6	Mg ²⁺ , 20	118.1, 118.3	19.5 ₀ , 19.5 ₉	-0.20, -0.05
19.6	Mn ²⁺ , 20	117.9, 117.9	19.5 ₃ , 19.5 ₆	-0.20, -0.20
19.6	In ³⁺ , 20	117.9, 117.6	19.5 ₈ , 19.4 ₇	-0.20, -0.52
22.4	Cr ³⁺ , 20	134.9, 134.9	22.3 ₈ , 22.3 ₆	-0.22, -0.22
22.4	Al ³⁺ , 20	134.8, 134.7	22.3 ₇ , 22.3 ₁	-0.35, -0.40

* in presence of Mg-EDTA.

loss in weight was 81.4%. The theoretical loss required for the conversion of $\text{Cd}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)_2$ to CdO is 81.1%.

Optimum pH and reagent concentration: Experiments under identical conditions using 19.6 mg of cadmium and 0.18 g of the reagent indicated the precipitation commenced at pH 6.5 and was complete between 6.8 and 8.5. At higher pH there was some contamination due to the reagent.

In another set of experiments with the same quantity of cadmium and identical precipitation pH (7.0), it was observed that after the quantitative precipitation of the complex the supernatant liquid should be at least 0.02% with respect to the reagent.

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